

VIBROTACTILE TEDDY BEAR: ENHANCING MUSICAL EXPERIENCES FOR CHILDREN WITH COCHLEAR NERVE DEFICIENCY THROUGH A VIBROTACTILE SOFT TOY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the potential of a soft toy prototype that integrates vibrotactile feedback and sound to enhance musical experiences for children with hearing impairments, particularly those with Auditory Neuropathy Spectrum Disorder (ANSD) and Cochlear Nerve Deficiency (CND). Traditional hearing aids and cochlear implants often fail to deliver the full spectrum of musical experiences, impacting children's development and quality of life. The soft toy provides vibrotactile feedback synchronized to music, allowing children to feel rhythm and harmonic content, creating an holistic musical experience.

The prototype, designed as a soft animal toy, includes a speaker and a vibrotactile motor controlled via Bluetooth. Two children with CND interacted with the toy during Auditory-Verbal Therapy (AVT) sessions. Observations showed varying engagement levels based on age and developmental stage. The younger child required redirection, while the older child was more focused.

Findings suggest that vibrotactile feedback in AVT can enhance auditory and emotional experience, highlighting the need for personalized, age-appropriate approaches and further research.

1. INTRODUCTION

For some young children with hearing challenges, significant barriers exist in accessing and enjoying music, affecting their overall development and quality of life. Traditional hearing aids (HAs) and cochlear implants (CIs) have made strides in improving speech comprehension, but they still fall short in delivering the full spectrum of musical experiences. Music, with its complex tones, rhythms, and emotional nuances, may be difficult for many HA and CI

users to fully appreciate due to limitations in frequency range, dynamic range, and timbre recognition [1].

Research has shown that music training can significantly improve music perception skills and overall well-being for children with hearing impairments [1–3]. This is particularly relevant for children with Auditory Neuropathy Spectrum Disorder (ANSD) and Cochlear Nerve Deficiency (CND), conditions characterized by an underdeveloped or absent cochlear nerve, which can lead to profound hearing loss. In particular, CND is often associated with very poor hearing performance, and cochlear implantation has been proven to be a viable improvement for children affected [4, 5]. Regardless of how auditory skills develop, the auditory signal provided is significantly weaker compared to a hearing system with a normal cochlear nerve. Consequently, the improvement must stem from the brain's ability to process this limited auditory signal from the cochlear implant. This explains why a longer period is needed, particularly for the development of speech perception [5]. Early intervention and personalized training are crucial for children with hearing loss, especially those with ANSD or CND. Thus, it is interesting to study how music can be enjoyed by children with conditions that disrupt neural activity and affect sound perception [6].

One technique that might lead to positive effects is the use of vibrotactile feedback to aid the hearing sense, which involves mapping audio signals to tactile vibrations to emphasize specific features such as pitch [7, 8]. By combining auditory and tactile stimuli, vibrotactile feedback can enhance sound awareness and music perception for children with hearing loss [9].

Auditory-Verbal Therapy (AVT) is an established tool for enhancing auditory skills and emotional well-being in children with hearing challenges. It has been shown that children who undergo a 3-year program improve emotional and behavioral problems, as well as social strengths, to the extent of being comparable with typically hearing peers [10]. Thus, by engaging multiple senses during AVT sessions, there is a possibility of obtaining a more holistic and enriching experience for individuals facing the most difficult hear-

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ing challenges. The choice of haptics over vision is driven by the AVT practice to prioritize sound: literature shows that vision tends to overpower other senses in cochlear implant recipients (the McGurk effect) [11]. By focusing on vibrotactile aids, we aimed to provide additional sensory input that supports auditory processing without taking over other senses.

To address these hurdles and facilitate the learning path of children with specific aetiologies, we propose a soft toy prototype that integrates haptic feedback and sound to enhance musical experiences. This toy is designed to provide vibrotactile feedback synchronized to music, allowing children to feel the rhythm and harmonic content of the music. By combining auditory and tactile stimuli, the toy aims to create a more immersive, multisensory, and enjoyable musical experience. We believe that technologies embedded in friendly and familiar objects such as toys can make the rehabilitation process more pleasant.

In this paper, we present the design of the prototype, the methodology of the study, the observations, and the discussion of the findings.

2. PROTOTYPE DESCRIPTION

The prototype is a soft toy shaped like a small animal, made of soft fabric and synthetic wool-like filling. The soft toy was modified by adding two *hook-and-loop fasteners* strips on the sides of a cut in the back, allowing access to the electronic circuit inside.

The electronic system provides sound and vibrotactile feedback, controllable via any music player capable of streaming sound through Bluetooth. The toy features a speaker located in the middle of the torso and a vibrotactile motor positioned in the front center of its body. The vibrotactile motor is a voice-coil (Tactuator BMIC from TactileLabs) that provides strong and broad-band vibrations. It is powered by a rechargeable battery, which can be charged through a USB port. The toy can be turned on and off using a switch located on its back.

2.1 First Design Iteration

In the first iteration, we integrated a stereo low-power Bluetooth receiver, the Sunrom M18¹, with a 3W stereo amplifier. The amplifier's outputs were connected to both a vibrotactile actuator and a mini 8 Ohm loudspeaker. Power was supplied by three 1.5V AA batteries in series configuration, providing a total of 4.5V. With this configuration, the loudspeaker and the actuator each received one of the two stereo output channels. Without proper configuration of the streaming device, the system would provide separate audio streams to the two actuators, according to how the music was mixed. Figure 1 illustrates the electronic circuit. The circuitry and loudspeaker were housed inside a cardboard box to protect the fragile components from impacts, while the vibrotactile actuator, enclosed in a 3D-printed case, was positioned in the front area of the stuffed animal's belly to deliver strong vibrations when the toy is hugged.

¹ Sunrom Bluetooth Transfer Module MX8, last accessed May 30, 2025

Figure 1. First iteration of the soft toy's circuitry

2.2 Second Design Iteration

In the second iteration, we integrated the Bluetooth receiver and the amplifier into a single module that also includes a charging circuit for handling a rechargeable LiPo battery. The board used is an ESP-32 A1S AudioKit, which we programmed to behave like a Bluetooth loudspeaker. It receives, decodes, and plays audio to both the loudspeaker and the haptic actuator. The new circuitry is shown in Figure 2. Additionally, we designed a simple 3D-printed enclosure to accommodate the entire system within the stuffed toy and protect the components from impacts. The software also allows for a dual-mono configuration, providing the exact same signal to both outputs, if needed.

Figure 2. Second iteration of the soft toy's circuitry.

The enclosure ensures the possibility to place the components in any medium-sized soft toy. Thus, the toy can be easily customized to fit the child's preferences. In addition, the programmable board allows for further customization such as real-time digital signal processing techniques to process sound and vibrations.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we will describe how the study was conducted, including the participants, the procedure, and the materials used.

3.1 Participants

We included two young children aged 2 years and 10 months, and 4 years and 5 months. From now on, the younger participant will be referred to as *Little Star*, and the older as *Bright Star*. Both children were diagnosed with

Figure 3. The first (a) and second (b) iterations of the soft toy's protective enclosure. In figure (a), it is possible to see the 3D-printed case containing the vibrotactile actuator.

hearing loss and cochlear nerve deficiency and were recipients of bilateral cochlear implants. In the case of Little Star, her parents struggled to keep the cochlear implants on, and as a result, they were not used full-time on a daily basis. At the time of the study, the two children were in their second year of AV therapy. They were recruited through the Copenhagen Hearing and Balance Center (CHBC) at Rigshospitalet, the largest hospital in Denmark. The study was approved by the ethical board of Rigshospitalet through the speech and language pathologists involved in the study. The participants were accompanied by their parents, who were informed about the study's purpose and procedures. The parents provided verbal consent, allowing their children to play and interact with the prototype during the AVT session.

3.2 Procedure

We arranged two sessions at the CHBC during their individual AVT program. This choice was made to include the AV therapist in the session, in order to provide a guided experience for the child. Moreover, the children had the chance to be introduced to new technology with a trusted and familiar person. Additionally, they were in the presence of their parents, as is typical for all AV sessions. The sessions were recorded using a video camera, and the children's reactions were noted by the researchers.

Figure 4. Children interact with the prototype under the supervision of the Auditory-Verbal therapist.

3.2.1 Participant Little Star

In the guided exploration at the hospital, the child was introduced to the soft toy and allowed to play with it for 15 minutes during the beginning of the AV session. During

this time, the child was encouraged to interact with the toy while music, typically used for therapeutic activities such as "Fem Små Aber", played through its loudspeaker and vibrotactile actuator. The child was invited to listen to the song, touch the soft toy, and feel the vibrations.

In a later iteration, we provided the child with the soft toy to take home for one and a half months. The child was encouraged to play with the toy and listen to music through it. The parents were instructed to use the teddy bear as a tool to engage the child in musical activities and to observe the child's reactions to the toy. At the end of this period, the parents had an informal conversation with the researchers to report their observations and experiences with the prototype.

3.2.2 Participant Bright Star

A similar approach to the one used with Little Star was adopted with Bright Star. The child was introduced to the soft toy during the AV session. This time, due to the older age of the participant, the AV therapist instructed the child to play a simple video game based on the 6 Ling sound identification task. The game, developed by one of the authors, was designed to train the child's listening skills in distinguishing sounds like "sh" and "ssss". The game was controlled through an iPad placed in front of Bright Star, while the child was hugging the soft toy. Bright Star was encouraged to listen to the sounds, touch the soft toy, and feel the vibrations to help him distinguish the sounds. Once the sound was assessed, the participant had to report the answer by touching the corresponding image on the iPad.

Figure 5. Interface of the video game for 6 Ling sound identification task.

4. OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

In this section, we present the observations and results of the study, including the children's reactions to the prototype and the parents' feedback. During the first interaction, Little Star showed curiosity and interest in the soft toy. She was eager to touch and hug it, and seemed to enjoy the vibrations. She was particularly drawn to the toy's belly, where the vibrotactile actuator was located. She laid her head on the toy's belly and showed surprise. Over the session, her interest expanded to the entire toy, and she began to play with it as if it were a regular stuffed animal.

The therapist, in accordance with the session's tasks, used the toy to engage the child in musical activities, such as

listening to songs and playing simple musical games involving wooden animals. In this specific activity, the soft toy served merely as a loudspeaker, as Little Star was supposed to interact with the wooden toys. Overall, she seemed to enjoy the activities and showed a positive reaction to the toy, even though her focus was not always on it. After the initial interest and surprise for the novel object, she seemed to lose interest in the soft toy, and the therapist had to redirect her attention to it. Due to her young age and possibly limited daily use of her cochlear implants, Little Star required guidance during the interaction, and the therapist had to redirect her attention several times.

In contrast, Bright Star, the older participant, showed a different reaction to the prototype. Bright Star was more focused and diligently held the toy on the chest while interacting with the iPad. This allowed him to feel the vibrations and hear the sounds while playing the game. Bright Star seemed engaged in the task, and the therapist did not have to redirect attention to the toy, as it was an integral part of the activity. The child showed a positive reaction to the entire experience.

The parents provided positive feedback about the prototype, noting that their children enjoyed interacting with it. Little Star's parents agreed to take the teddy bear home to allow her more opportunities to play with it and engage with the sound features. In particular, Little Star's parents reported that their child played a lot with the teddy bear during the period at home, also sharing it with her brother. At the time of return, the toy had been broken due to extensive and intensive use.

5. DISCUSSION

In this small study, we observed a significant difference in the reactions to the soft toy from the two children with CNL. Little Star, the younger participant, showed initial interest and curiosity in the toy but quickly lost focus and needed redirection from the therapist. Bright Star, the older participant, was more focused and engaged with it, using the teddy bear as a tool to hear and feel the sound stimuli. These differences can be attributed to the children's age and developmental stage, as well as their familiarity with technology and toys. Additionally, age highlights differences in attention span, comprehension, and ability to follow instructions between the two children.

These observations suggest that toy design, as well as the activities connected to it, should be tailored to different developmental stages to ensure engagement and effectiveness in AVT sessions for children with CNL. The vibrotactile feedback might assume different roles and meanings according to the participants' age. For instance, the vibrotactile feedback might be more engaging for older children who can understand the connection between sound and vibration, perceiving details and nuances, while younger children might benefit from it as a confirmation of sound presence. Furthermore, familiarity with the toy might change the engagement over time, as the child becomes more accustomed to it and its features. This suggests that the toy should be introduced gradually, allowing the child time to explore and interact with it at their own pace. Additionally, due

to the rapid development in children, the design needs to be adapted to their specific needs at the moment and be capable of modification and upgrades over time. This might become an expensive issue for toys that require sophisticated technology.

From the literature, we know that multisensory integration between sound and vibrotactile feedback might be beneficial for cochlear implant recipients, as it conveys additional information that can support the listening experience [12, 13]. Further research should explore different ways to integrate and map vibrotactile feedback in AVT practices. Mappings have been shown to be crucial in the effectiveness of vibrotactile feedback, as they can highlight specific features of the sound [7, 8].

Another consideration is the integration of the prototype into AVT practices. The therapist's role is crucial in facilitating effective use of the device, as they can guide the child in the interaction and ensure that the toy is used correctly. The therapist can also provide feedback to the parents on how to use the toy at home and integrate it into the child's daily play routine. This requires a plan from the therapist on how to design the training interaction and find suitable activities that can easily include the use of a soft toy that provides vibrotactile feedback. The clinical integration of such a device is an interesting topic as well. The design process should take into account the challenges brought by the use of equipment in a clinical environment, considering safety, sanitization, and ease of use as core characteristics. Ultimately, one of the core strengths of AVT lies in its emphasis on guiding and coaching parents. Every session should include strategies for transferring activities into the home environment. The overarching goal of AVT is to ensure that all training is functional and applicable in everyday listening situations.

From a clinical perspective, engaging children with CNL in AVT sessions can be challenging due to a limited auditory access and limited attention span compared to children with a regular sensorineural hearing loss. Integrating both the auditory and tactile sense in the therapy showed to be very positive and more engaging for the children. When demonstrating the toy we experienced that both children showed interest in the listening task and maintained focus when we kept the activity short and implemented toys relevant to their developmental stage in language and play level.

Conducting studies with a larger and more diverse group of participants would help validate the findings and explore the toy's effectiveness across different age groups and hearing conditions. Implementing longitudinal studies would allow researchers to assess the long-term impact of the toy on auditory and multisensory development, as well as its integration into daily routines. However, the group of children with CNL is small and very heterogeneous, and vibrotactile feedback is not necessary for the vast majority of children with hearing challenges who undergo the AVT program.

The role of vibrotactile feedback in AVT is still underexplored, as most newer generations of children with cochlear implants acquire hearing capabilities comparable to their typically hearing peers. However, the contribution of vi-

brotactile feedback might be beneficial for children who present more hearing challenges, as seen with our two participants.

5.1 Limitations of the Study

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. Firstly, the small sample size of only two participants limits the generalizability of the findings. A larger sample size would provide more robust data and allow for more comprehensive conclusions. Secondly, the study was conducted over a relatively short period, with limited interaction time with the prototype. Longer-term studies are needed to assess the sustained impact and effectiveness of the toy.

Additionally, the two participants were at different developmental stages, which may have influenced their interactions with the toy and made comparisons difficult. This is mainly due to the rarity of the hearing aetiologies we took into consideration during the recruitment process. Future studies should consider a more homogeneous group or cover a larger sample for developmental variability. The activities conducted during the study were specific to the AVT sessions and may not encompass the full range of potential uses for the toy. Exploring a wider variety of activities could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the toy's effectiveness.

5.2 Future Work

Based on the findings and limitations of this study, directions for future research are proposed.

Investigating ways to customize the toy to better suit individual preferences and needs, such as independently adjustable vibration intensity and different types of vibrotactile feedback, could enhance its effectiveness. Technological advancements, such as integrating more sophisticated sensors, enhancing the quality of vibrotactile feedback, and developing interactive features that respond to the child's actions, should also be explored.

Studying the practical aspects of integrating the toy into clinical settings, including safety, sanitization, and ease of use, is crucial to ensure it meets the standards required for therapeutic devices. Developing training programs for parents and therapists to effectively use the toy and integrate it into AVT practices would ensure consistent and beneficial use.

6. CONCLUSION

In this study, we explored the potential of a soft toy prototype that integrates haptic feedback and sound to enhance musical experiences for children with hearing challenges. The prototype was designed to provide vibrotactile feedback synchronized to music, allowing children to feel the rhythm and harmonic content of the music. Our observations indicated that the toy was well-received by the children, with varying levels of engagement and interaction based on their age and developmental stage.

The findings suggest that the integration of vibrotactile feedback in AVT sessions is a viable path for making the

sessions more holistic and engaging for children with CND. However, the study also highlighted the need for personalized and age-appropriate approaches to maximize the effectiveness of such interventions.

Future research should focus on a wider range of activities and contexts. Additionally, technological advancements and customization options should be investigated to better suit individual preferences and needs. The practical aspects of integrating the toy into clinical settings and developing training programs for parents and therapists are also important areas for further exploration.

Overall, this study provides a preliminary foundation for the development of multisensory tools that can support the auditory and emotional development of children with specific hearing aetiologies.

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